

Perceived Influence of Flexible Work Arrangement (Compressed Work) on Employee Performance in Food and Beverage Companies in Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the Perceived Influence of Flexible Work Arrangement (Compressed Work) on Employee Performance in Food and Beverage Companies in Rivers State, Nigeria. To achieve the purpose of the study, the researcher developed three objectives of the study and research questions that guided the study. The study made use of descriptive survey design. The target population was employees from fifteen (15) food and beverage firms in Nigeria. The sample size of the survey study was 224 questionnaires returned from the employees' respondents of the fifteen (15) selected food and beverage firms in Rivers state. The result showed that JR has low relationship with to employee effectiveness, innovativeness and efficiency. CW has a very strong relationship with employee effectiveness but has very low relationship with innovativeness and efficiency. The study recommended that the management of manufacturing Companies should always for the sake of effectiveness of work and the management of the manufacturing Companies not only food and beverage manufacturing Companies should always organize workshops and seminar to introduce skills and concept to actualize creativity in form of Innovativeness in every aspect to encourage employees' performance.

Key Words: Flexible, Work Arrangement, Employee Performance, Food and Beverage, Companies, Perceived, Influence, Compressed Work

INTRODUCTION

Employee performance rests on efficient and effective performance of discrete workers who work in an organization. An organization therefore, looks up to their staff performance to gain high performance. Flexible working arrangements are actually emerging issues in human resource management field. The world is becoming a global village; hence as an employee in any organization the balance between personal life and work responsibilities should not be ignored, if the employee performance is to be achieved (Hill, 2021). In the current global work environment, there is intense competition for talented employees and for market share based on higher product quality and lower prices in order to realize strategic advantage. Competition requires organizations to take into account diversity of employee's needs, work life values, cultural influences in the areas where the companies operate as well as the diversity of working relationships in order to attract,

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retain and fully engage the employee. As many organizations come to terms with the challenges of attracting and retaining the best talent and retaining the best talent coupled with the emerging issues of work life conflicts, it is important that managers employ a variety of human resource practices to attain organizational goals (McLean & Collins., 2021).

In response to these concerns, and increasing demand for work-life balance from employees, companies have been introducing initiatives such as Flexible Working Arrangements (FWA), where employees can choose their place of work, and within boundaries their of scheduled hours of work. These FWA's can lead to higher levels of job satisfaction, organisational commitment, and intention to stay with the company. Flexible work time arrangements are essentially those arrangements of work that allows workers to modify where, when and for how long job-related work is performed (Lewis, 2013).

There is therefore a perceived imbalance between the demands of current lives and people's abilities to adequately cope with them and this may lead to an experience of stress. In a society filled with conflicting responsibilities and commitments, flexible work arrangement has become a predominant issue in the workplace. Three major factors contribute to the interest in and importance of serious consideration of flexible work arrangement: global competition, renewed interest in personal lives, family values and an aging workforce. It is against this background that this study examined the perceived influence of flexible work arrangement (compressed work) on employee performance in food and beverage companies in Rivers State, Nigeria.

Concept of Flexible Work Arrangement

Flexible work practices as stated by Hill (2021) allow employees the freedom to work outside the standard work schedules. According to Rau (2013) flexible work practices are different forms of working schedule that enables employees to work outside the normal work day. Some of various forms of flexible work practices include – telecommuting, compressed hours, shift, flexi-time and annualized hours. However, this study was interested in only four types of flexible work practices namely: telecommuting, compressed work week, Job Rotation and flexi-time.

According Tang and Dermid (2018) is of the view that workforce preferred flexible work and this would take priority when looking for new employment. Organizations are more alert and seek to engage employees who are more creative. They therefore look for ways and means of attracting employees. The concept of FWAs as a human resources management practice was introduced in 1967 at a German Aerospace Company as a means to minimize absenteeism. The introduction of FWAs from this period onwards has brought a complete turnaround in bringing more and more women in workplaces that has been previously dominated by men as a result of benefiting from flexible arrangements. The broad framework that guided the notion of FWAs in organizational setting is Jon Atkinson's Flexible Firm model (a technique for organizing human resources using various forms of workplace flexibility) that was first proposed in 1986. Flexible working is now considered as smart working - one of the approaches that drive greater efficiency and effectiveness.

Flexible working arrangement can be defined in different forms. It is a human resources management practice that allows employees of an organization in making informed choices about when, where and for how long they undertake work-related responsibilities. Flexible working arrangement is also defined as an “alternative work options that allow work to be accomplished outside of the traditional temporal and/or spatial boundaries of a standard workday” (Rau & Hyland, 2022). It refers to work arrangements not bound by physical confines of a traditional office location, it is rather the scheduling of work hours and workweeks not limited by spatial borders. In this work pattern, employees are allowed to adjust their schedule and workplace.

Dimensions of Independent Variable (Flexible Work Arrangement)

Compressed Work

Compressed work is an agreement in which employees’ works for more hours by prolonging the length of work days in a week (Sundo & Fujii., 2015). Employees may opt to work for four days in a week to get a day off. Poor., (2020) ascertains that the commonly type of compressed hours is made up of ten hours per day making forty hours for 4 days. The employee could therefore be in a position to take a day off either Monday or Friday. Compressed work has limitations. Work may be disrupted if most employees are absent due to emergencies since it would be difficult to provide for employees to alternate; Employees health may be affected as a result of working for long hours; Meetings and training of employees may also be affected due to different work schedules; Managers may also fail to provide supervision when employees work for extended hours.

Compressed Work is another form of scheduling method that allows employees to work a standard workweek of 40 hours compressed into fewer than five days in one week (CRANET., 2006; Strategic Human Resources Management SHRM., 2020). The concept of compressed workweek (the working modality of 4 days a week) became popular in 1970’s in which companies claimed great results and more businesses began to use them (Bird, 2020). According to Bird, ‘interest in compressed workweek [modality] peaked in 1973’ (Bird, 2020). In this scheduling, the workweek is reduced than the standard days by increasing the number of hours an employee is required to work each day. For example, instead of the standard five 8-hour days week, employees can work for four 10-hours days. In this modality, employees work fulltime in a few whereas longer days.

The most common forms of compressed workweek is 4/40 - employees work 10 hours daily in 4 days of the week and they will be able to take either Friday or Monday off, enabling employees to extend their weekend to 3 days. This arrangement entails ‘an extra day off in the middle of the week, a weekend work day with two weekdays off, or rotating days off to share the three-day weekend across the workforce’ (Bird., 2020).

Compressed work is commonly used in manufacturing settings due to the interdependence nature of the work in assembly lines and the fact that manufacturing organizations might not require employees to be present at regular time intervals. Moreover, in comparison to other FWAs such as flextime and telecommuting, compressed workweek arrangement is claimed to be less desirable by employees (Rahman., 2019).

In view of a quantitative (meta-analysis) study done in 1999, compressed workweek is indicated to have positive relationship to both the job satisfaction and satisfaction with work schedule. It is also asserted in this study that the key features of a job including responsibility, autonomy and job knowledge emanated from implementing compressed workweek might be related with more positive attitudes toward the job itself. Such positive changes would lead to higher job satisfaction. In view of this empirical study, the extent of behavioral work related criteria such as absenteeism and productivity were lower than attitudinal work-related criteria such as job satisfaction when compared to the findings of flextime schedule. On the contrary, a recent study done in 2008 showed a positive relationship with productivity of employees working a 4/40 compressed week schedule but the finding reported that these employees did not have greater job satisfaction. In conclusion, compressed workweek allows employees to exercise certain form of autonomy in managing their time, it increases their job responsibility and knowledge which are positive indicators of employees' attitude towards their job. And, these positive organizational outcomes are correlated with employee job satisfaction. As discussed above, the extent of the provision of compressed workweek on job satisfaction might be lower than that of flextime schedule. Nevertheless, compressed workweek schedule does positively affect employee job satisfaction.

Concept of Employee Performance

Company performance is the outcome achieved in meeting internal and external goals of a Company (Lin, 2018). Performance has several outcomes including growth, survival, success and competitiveness. Better performing employees at work become more committed to their organizations and ultimately contribute to increased organizational performance as well as growth of the economy. Marko and Sridevi., (2020) measured that well performing employees are considered with high motivation and values to ensure positive outcome in their organization.

An attractive and supportive working environment provide conditions that enable employees to perform effectively, making best use of their knowledge, skills and competences and the available resources in order to provides high-quality of organizational service. Based on this study, the factors are explained below. The physical working environment can make a person to fit or misfit to the environment of the workplace. A physical work environment can also be known as an ergonomic workplace. Researches on the workplace environment need to be done in order to get an ergonomic workplace for each of the employees. By having this ergonomic physical workplace at their workplace, it will help employees from not getting the nerve injury (Cooper &Dewe, 2014).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Companies experience employees dissatisfied with their jobs, they are thought to perform less and more prone to absenteeism. Organizations project these in their employment directly and or indirectly through allied services to the business. It is therefore imperative that the welfare of the staff working in these companies are given paramount importance by both managers and the Companies' stakeholders as a whole. For many employees today both male and female lives are becoming more consumed with a host of family and other personal responsibilities and interests in

addition to demands of the workplace. Therefore, a one of the problem is the perceived imbalance between the demands of current lives and people's abilities to adequately cope with them, which lead to unnecessary stress (World of Work Report., 2011).

The venture sector is now under pressure to ensure decent working conditions for their employees. The relationship between labour relationship practices and the management in the venture sector is not a bed of roses. Therefore, considering the previous studies ideology, none considered the role of Job Rotation, compressed work and flex time in enhancing employee performance. This is because Flexible working relationship in an organizations working arrangement relative to time, working location and pattern of working. part time, shift work, compressed work hours and Job Rotation are considered in this present study, and it is gap or a departure in this current study.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of this study is to examine the perceived influence of flexible work arrangement on employee performance in food and beverage companies in Rivers State, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

1. Determine the extent compressed work relates to employee's effectiveness in food and beverage Companies in Rivers State.
2. Ascertain the extent compressed work (stress, autonomy and less secure) relates to Innovativeness (trust, curiosity and experimentation) in food and beverage Companies in Rivers State.
3. Examine the extent compressed work relates to efficiency in food and beverage Companies in Rivers State.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

In an attempt to accomplish the aim of this study, the following research questions where adopted:

1. To what extent does compressed work relates to employee's effectiveness in food and beverage Companies in Rivers State.
2. To what extent does compressed work (stress, autonomy and less secure) relates to Innovativeness (trust, curiosity and experimentation) in food and beverage Companies in Rivers State.
3. To what extent does compressed work relates to efficiency in food and beverage Companies in Rivers State.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive correlational research design to examine Perceived Influence of Flexible Work Arrangement (Compressed Work) on Employee Performance in Food and Beverage Companies in Rivers State, Nigeria. The population of this study consist of Five Hundred and Eight (508) employees of the fifteen (15) food and beverage firms in Rivers State of Nigeria that are registered with NAFDAC. The researcher adopted a stratified sampling method because the number of the total management employees of each selected listed consumer goods manufacturing

companies have been grouped (strata). The researcher made use of simple random technique to select the samples contained in each group (stratum). The main instrument applied was questionnaire. The questionnaire was designed following standard guidelines for questionnaire design. The initial component of the questionnaire embraced the demographic background of the respondents, while the second component constituted 24 item-questions answered in Likert scale format, which measured relevant constructs. The data relating to the subject area of consideration were analyzed using relevant statistical tool, such as Descriptive Statistics to observe the characteristics of the variable and Spearman Rank Correlation since the researcher intends to delineate the level of relationship between independent and dependent variable, therefore, this tool is appropriate for the analysis.

RESULTS

Table 1 Compressed Works

S/NO	DESCRIPTION	VHE	HE	ME	LE	Total
(B)	Part time work lowers stress related complaints by an employee	55	97	45	27	224
	Part time work determines the number of tasks an employee performs in a given period	55	97	41	31	224
	Part time employment in health care provides less autonomy to the employees which affects the number of workload employee performs.	48	105	39	32	224
	Part time working determines employee performance in given period	45	107	39	33	224
	Total	203	406	164	123	896
	Averages	50	102	41	31	224
	Percentages	23	45	18	14	100

Source: Field survey 2024.

From the table 1 203(23%) strongly agree, 406(45) agree, 164(18%) disagree and 123 (14) strongly disagree on compressed work.

Table 2 Employee Effectiveness

S/N O	DESCRIPTION	VHE	HE	ME	LE	Total
(D)	A temporary contract influences the number of employees entering the organization at a given period.	63	96	29	36	224
	Temporary contracts influence the number of employees moving out of the organization at a given period.	57	95	37	35	224
	Temporary contracts attracts employees with new knowledge which influences ability of employees in the organization	47	108	39	30	224
	Temporary contracts attracts employees with new skills which influences ability of employees in the organization	60	134	20	10	224
	Total	227	433	125	111	896
	Averages	57	108	31	28	224
	Percentages	25	48	14	13	100

Source: Field survey 2024.

From the table 2, 227(25%) strongly agree, 433(48%) agree, 125(14%) disagree, and 111 (13) strongly disagree on employee effectiveness.

Table 3 Innovativeness

S/N O	DESCRIPTION	VHE	HE	ME	LE	Total
(E)	Does Innovativeness on policy of a Company improve the Job Rotation techniques	64	91	37	32	224
	Technological Innovativeness has it impacted on Job Rotation or work shift	58	96	37	33	224
	Does Innovativeness on compressed work affect the employees performance	49	109	34	32	224

	Innovativeness on employees attitude to work trigger improved flex time	43	107	40	34	224
	Total	214	403	148	131	896
	Averages	53	101	37	33	224
	Percentages	24	45	16	15	100

Source: Field survey 2024.

From the table 3, 214(24%) strongly agree, 403(45%) agree, 148(16%) disagree and 131 (15%) strongly disagree on innovativeness.

Table 4 Efficiency

S/N O	DESCRIPTION	VHE	HE	ME	LE	Total
(F)	Increased productivity is influenced by number of actual patients compared to desired number in the organization.	65	90	34	35	224
	Customer satisfaction is influenced by the number customer care staff in the organization.	55	96	39	34	224
	Job satisfaction is linked to the number of days an employee attends work	50	101	39	34	224
	Employee turnover is influenced by the number of employees moving into and leaving the organization in a given period	53	98	40	33	224
	Total	223	385	152	136	896
	Averages	56	96	38	34	224
	Percentages	25	43	17	15	100

Source: Field survey 2024.

From the table 4, 223(25%) strongly agree, 385(43%) agree, 152(17%) disagree and 136 (15%) strongly disagree on efficiency.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Based on the findings, discussions are made on the study: Compressed work has a positive significant relationship with employee effectiveness of food and beverage manufacturing

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Companies in Rivers State. This is because there is no monotonous of work of food and beverage manufacturing Companies in Rivers State due to rotation of job, compressed work has a positive insignificant relation with innovativeness of food and beverage manufacturing Companies in Rivers State. This is because compressed work approach is not a form of ideological innovativeness and compressed work has a positive insignificant relationship with efficiency of food and beverage manufacturing Companies in Rivers State. This could be due to chronic inflation ravaging the Nigerian economy where the concept of efficiency in production has been negatively affected.

CONCLUSION

Based on the empirical analysis, the researchers' concluded the followings: There is a positive and insignificant influence of compressed work on employees' effectiveness of food and beverage Companies in Rivers State, there is a positive significant influence of compressed work on innovativeness of food and beverage Companies in Rivers State and that there is a positive insignificant influence of compressed work on efficiency of food and beverage Companies in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommends the following:

1. The management of manufacturing Companies should always for the sake of effectiveness of work.
2. The management of the manufacturing Companies not only food and beverage manufacturing Companies should always organize workshops and seminar to introduce skills and concept to actualize creativity in form of Innovativeness in every aspect to encourage employees' performance.
3. The policy of the Companies should in encompasses the care and welfare of the workers to motivate them in becoming very efficient in carry out the duties to enhance their performance and ensure sustainability of the entity's continual survival.

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